

Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften. A visual interface of processes and innovations

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With the current and emerging outputs of digital (humanistic) research, such as databases, code or 3D visualizations, the boundaries of traditional journal and book publishing formats are being pushed. This poster uses a flowchart to visualize the publication process of a Diamond Open Access journal, the *Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften* (ZfdG)¹ (Journal for Digital Humanities), published by the *Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel* (HAB). This approach makes inherent editorial processes transparent, creates opportunities for feedback from the scholarly community regarding workflows and options, and enables critical reflection.

SeDOA Innovation Lab

In close cooperation with the *SeDOA Innovation Lab* (SIL), the *HAB* provides its Diamond OA journal as a testing ground for the implementation of promising innovative features. *SIL* is tasked with identifying the needs and publication practices of the German scholarly community wishing to publish in Diamond OA. It is embedded in the DFG-funded *Servicestelle Diamond Open Access* (SeDOA)² (German Diamond Capacity Center), which aims to optimize, coordinate, and innovate Diamond publishing services.

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The approach taken by the *ZfdG* is centered on quality assurance and transparency: a pre-peer review desk review is applied; furthermore, submitters may select from three peer review models: closed peer review (pre-publication), open peer review (post-publication) or open public peer review.³ To further enhance transparency, the content of the respective reviews of the open peer review is published, depending on the reviewers' decision. The current workflow allows for the publication of revised versions, ensuring ongoing quality improvement. In line with its dedication to quality assurance, the *ZfdG* recently implemented provisions to make the research and data-creation processes transparent, an element essential in the digital humanities (Pielström et al. 2024). To further the visibility of research data, facilitate greater reproducibility and sustainability of research in line with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Baillet 2024; Jansky and de la Iglesia 2023; de la Iglesia et al. 2025), the *ZfdG* has begun publishing Data Papers as a new format. While the first four Data Papers have been published, additional ones are scheduled for publication at the beginning of 2026.

The multi-stage editorial workflow begins, once the manuscript has been submitted. The process includes editorial revisions and bibliographic editing in coordination with the authors, as well as file markup, metadata maintenance and cataloguing. This process is managed through a Git-based ticket and versioning system with a largely automated XML-based workflow using custom scripts and transformation schemes: The article is made available as a browser-based reading version, downloadable as PDF and XML, provided with a DOI, cataloged at DOAJ⁴, tracked via BEACON and deposited in a Zotero library.

Visual exploration of publication paths

Narrative visualizations communicate data stories, in this case a publication workflow. Interactivity⁵ plays a key role,

shaping the user's experience by connecting story components and opening up paths (Morini et al. 2025). The interface concept, developed at the *UCLAB* (University of Applied Sciences Potsdam), seeks to provide an intuitive way for users to actively navigate complex processes. The concept in use, the *Interactive Flowchart*⁶, which is available as a free reusable template on GitHub, combines progressive disclosure of the information, a narrative and exploration. The conference presentation will be available on paper, as well as through navigation elements via a screen. The visualization has several aims: The visual representation allows for an exploration of the editorial and publication process from the contributors' perspective. It furthermore opens up space for scholarly feedback and critical reflection on process steps and the overall procedures.

Outlook

Not only does the poster invite reflection and comments on the publication process, but it also aims to reveal the challenges that the introduction of new formats entails. This interactive user guide showcases a Diamond OA publishing workflow and invites the community to simulate, evaluate, and discuss the overall publication process, the published Data Papers, and their respective reviews. This is of particular interest to *SIL*, which identifies needs and innovation potential in order to develop ideas further and make them available to the broader research community.

Footnotes

1. <https://zfdg.de/>.
2. <https://diamond-open-access.de/en/sedoa/>.
3. <https://zfdg.de/r-wie-review-verfahren>.
4. <https://doaj.org/toc/2510-1358>.
5. Interactivity for visualization is defined by Dimara and Perin (2020), as “the interplay between a person and a data interface involving a data-related intent”.
6. <https://uclab.fh-potsdam.de/projects/interactive-flow-chart>, <https://github.com/uclab-potsdam/interactive-flow-chart>. See an example of implementation focussing on a climate topic: <https://flowchart.bettercatastrophe.com/>.

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